

Enhancement Entrepreneurial Readiness for Vocational High School Students in Terms of Transferable Skills, Competency Skills and Interest in Entrepreneurship

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ABSTRACT: The focus in this article is to reveal enhancement entrepreneurial readiness for high school students in terms of transferable skills, competency skills and interest in entrepreneurship. The design of this study uses quantitative correlational. The results of this study (1) There is a significant contribution of transferable skills, expertise competencies and interest in entrepreneurship to entrepreneurial readiness that is equal to 63.2%, (2) There is a significant contribution of transferable skills to entrepreneurial readiness that is equal to 26.1%. (3) There is a significant contribution of expertise competence to entrepreneurial readiness that is equal to 8.3%. (4) There is a significant contribution of interest in entrepreneurship to entrepreneurial readiness that is equal to 28.8%.

KEYWORDS: Competency Skills, Entrepreneurial Interest, Entrepreneurial Readiness, Transferable Skills.

INTRODUCTION

Vocational education is part of the national education system that has the aim to produce graduates who have the skills and knowledge in accordance with the needs and requirements needed by the field of employment. Vocational High School (SMK) is a form of vocational education organized by the government to produce quality resources that are skilled and ready to work in the business or industrial world.

Law Number 20 Year 2003 Article 26 Paragraph 5 emphasizes that like courses or training, vocational graduates are directed at three main pillars namely (1) working in the business and industrial world (DU / DI), (2) working independently or own business, and (3) continue their studies to the tertiary level, especially professional or vocational tertiary institutions. In accordance with one of the objectives of the SMK which is working independently or own business can be interpreted as an independent entrepreneur and help create jobs for others. Mukhadis states that in terms of the substance and orientation of the demands of results, vocational education as a vehicle in an effort to facilitate the development of individual or group skills to be able to play a role as a creator or opening a job (job creator) [1].

According to the Central Statistics Agency/Badan Pusat Statistik (CSA/BPS) in August 2017 [2], the number of open unemployment was around 7 million people. The biggest percentage of unemployed from education level is (1) SMA: 27%; (2) SMK: 23%; (3) SMP: 18%; (4) SD: 13%; and (5) Higher Education: 12%, of which the number can be seen that there are still many unemployed graduates from SMK. Until now, the unemployment rate by the SMK group is included in the high category.

The high unemployment rate is caused by several factors. One of the factors causing the high unemployment rate is the mindset and attitude of the people who still think that work as permanent employees will guarantee better survival compared to other jobs [3]. This mindset has an impact on the lack of community interest to build and develop entrepreneurship.

The focus in this article is to reveal enhancement entrepreneurial readiness for high school students in terms of transferable skills, competency skills and interest in entrepreneurship.

METHODS

The design of this study uses quantitative correlational. The independent variables of this study are transferable expertise (X1), expertise competence (X2), and entrepreneurial interest (X3), while the research variable is about entrepreneurship readiness (Y). The model of the relationship between these variables is agreed in Figure.

Figure 1. Conceptual Model of Relationships between Variables

This research will be conducted at State Vocational School 11 Malang, State Vocational School 6 Malang, State Vocational School 1 Singosari, and State Vocational School 1 Kepanjen in Malang regency and city. The object of the research is known the number of students with engineering engineering programs, light vehicle engineering, and motorcycle engineering at the school as many as 610 students.

The research instrument is a tool used by researchers to capture or retrieve the research data needed [4]. Data that has been collected in this study is used in testing the exposure of hypotheses. The instrument in this study was used to obtain four groups of research data, namely: (1) transferable skills; (2) expertise competence; (3) interest in entrepreneurship; and (4) entrepreneurship readiness. In developing an instrument there are several stages, namely: (1) preparation of indicator variables to be examined; (2) compilation of the research instrument grids; and (3) implementation of research instrument trials namely validity and reliability testing.

Before the instrument was used, the instrument was tested. The trial of the instrument was conducted to see the validity and reliability of the instrument. The following will be presented an instrument grid of variable transferable skills, entrepreneurial interest, and entrepreneurial readiness.

RESULTS

The F test aims to test the first hypothesis, namely the effect of independent variables simultaneously on the dependent variable. In this test, it will be seen the effect of transferable skills, expertise competencies, and entrepreneurial interest simultaneously on entrepreneurial readiness. The F test results are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Test Results F

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	37832,835	3	12610,945	135,494	,000 ^b
	Residual	22058,476	237	93,074		
	Total	59891,311	240			

a. Dependent Variable: kesiapan berwirausaha

b. Predictors: (Constant), transferable skill, kompetensi keahlian, minat berwirausaha

Table 1 shows that the results of the hypothesis test can be seen from the calculated F value of 135.494 (p <0.05). With the provisions of H0 or the null hypothesis is rejected if the sig value <0.05, it can be seen that the results listed in Table 4.11 indicate that the significance value of 0.000 means <0.05, so that the results obtained that Ho is rejected and Ha is accepted. So the

transferable skill variable, expertise competency, and entrepreneurial interest have a simultaneous influence on entrepreneurial readiness.

Analysis of the coefficient of determination (R square) is used to see how much the percentage of the effect of the transferable skill variable, expertise competency, entrepreneurial interest together to the entrepreneurial readiness variable. The calculation results for the analysis of the coefficient of determination are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Results of the Determination Coefficient Analysis

Model	Model Summary ^b			
	R	R Squares	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	,795 ^a	,632	,627	9,647

a. Dependent Variable: kesiapan berwirausaha

b. Predictors: (Constant), *transferable skill*, kompetensi keahlian, minat berwirausaha

Table 2 shows that the R square value of 0.632, which means that the variable transferable skills, competency skills, entrepreneurial interest together have an influence on entrepreneurial readiness of 63.2%. While the remaining 36.8% entrepreneurship readiness is influenced by other factors outside this study.

Multiple regression analysis in this study was conducted to test the hypothesis, namely the influence of the independent variable (X) on the dependent variable (Y). In this analysis will be tested how much influence the independent variable transferable skills (X1), competence expertise (X2), entrepreneurial interest (X3) on entrepreneurial readiness (Y). The results of the multiple linear regression analysis are shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Results of Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Model	Coefficients ^a							
	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Correlations		
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Zero-order	Partial	Part
(Constant)	-57,162	8,035		-7,114	,000			
<i>transferable skill</i>	,520	,076	,370	6,869	,000	,707	,407	,271
1 kompetensi keahlian	,220	,074	,147	2,972	,000	,565	,190	,117
minat berwirausaha	,757	,109	,396	6,934	,000	,727	,411	,273

a. Dependent Variable: kesiapan berwirausaha

The multiple linear regression equation for three independent variables is as follows:

$$Y' = b_0 + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3$$

The dominant influence test is done to see how much the percentage of effective contribution of each independent variable to the dependent variable. The results of the effective contribution test are shown in Table 4 Whereas the formula used to calculate the dominant influence is:

$$SE = Beta \times Zero Order \times 100\%$$

Table 4. Results of Effective Donation Tests

Varibel	Beta	Zero Order	SE (%)
<i>Transferable Skill (X₁)</i>	0,370	0,707	26,1%
Kompetensi Keahlian (X ₂)	0,147	0,565	8,3%
Minat Berwirausaha (X ₃)	0,396	0,727	28,8%
Jumlah			63,2%

DISCUSSIONS

Effect of Transferable Skills on Entrepreneurial Readiness

The results of data analysis show that transferable skills have a positive (direct) effect on entrepreneurial readiness. Based on the results of the study, it appears that transferable skills have an almost dominant influence on vocational students' entrepreneurial readiness. This can be seen in the SE (effective contribution) provided by transferable skills has a value of 26.1%. The result is an effective contribution value that disputes 2.7% compared to the entrepreneurial interest variable, so it can be said that this variable has the greatest influence on entrepreneurial readiness after the entrepreneurial interest variable.

Based on the results of the analysis, it can be seen that if the transferable skills of students are getting better, then the entrepreneurship readiness of students will also be higher. Conversely, if transferable skills possessed by students are poor, then the entrepreneurship readiness of students will also be lower. This is consistent with the statement made by Berg [5] that to achieve the needs of the job market that is very closely related to technological development requires vocational education graduates who are able to adapt quickly to their technical competence and mastery of the technological environment. From the statement implies that transferable skills are identical to the adaptable abilities that must be possessed by vocational students, because if vocational students do not have transferable skills, the student concerned will lose out in competition. This happens due to market needs that continue to grow. In addition, the technology available at this time also continues to experience progress. So that vocational students must be prepared to accept these changes and progress.

Effect of Expertise Competency on Entrepreneurial Readiness

The results of data analysis show that expertise competencies have a positive (directional) effect on entrepreneurial readiness. Based on the results of the study, it appears that expertise competencies have the least effect on entrepreneurship readiness of vocational students. This can be seen in the SE (effective contribution) provided by the expertise competency has a value of 8.3%. This result is the lowest effective contribution value compared to the other two variables, so it can be said that this variable has the least effect on entrepreneurial readiness.

From the statement above, it can be seen that if students have good competency skills, students will be better prepared in entrepreneurship. Conversely, if the competency of expertise possessed by students is bad, students will find it difficult to prepare themselves for entrepreneurship. This is consistent with the statement made by Astiti & Margunani [6] that expertise competencies directly contribute to students' readiness in entrepreneurship.

Competence is closely related to skills. Therefore, students in understanding vocational education in Vocational Schools must be able to optimize their time to get all the experience and basic knowledge which can then be developed continuously. When associated with readiness in entrepreneurship, the experience and basic knowledge must be able and present in responding to the needs of the community. This is in line with Clarke & Winch [7] and Cahyanti & Indriayu [8] also emphasizes that the existence of vocational education is aimed at honing competencies which then ends in efforts to fulfill employment, maintenance, acceleration and improvement of the quality of the workforce so that they are able to answer challenges increase in community productivity.

The Effect of Entrepreneurial Interest on Entrepreneurial Readiness

The results of data analysis show that entrepreneurial interest has a positive (directional) effect on entrepreneurial readiness. Based on the results of the study, it appears that interest in entrepreneurship has a dominant influence on entrepreneurship readiness of vocational students. This can be seen in the SE (effective contribution) given by entrepreneurial interest has a value of 28.8%. The result is the highest effective contribution value compared to the other two variables, so it can be said that this variable has a dominant influence on entrepreneurial readiness.

Based on the results of the analysis that has been submitted, a conclusion can be drawn that if students have an interest in good entrepreneurship, then these students will be better prepared in entrepreneurship. Conversely, if students do not have an interest in entrepreneurship, then these students will experience difficulties in entrepreneurship. The results of this study are supported by Irsyada et al., [8] which states that there is a positive relationship between entrepreneurial interest and entrepreneurial readiness.

Bringing up an interest is not necessarily born by itself, it takes courage and perseverance to pioneer it. This is consistent with the statement made by Hisrich et al., [9] that in creating something new and valuable requires a hard effort and time that is not small, the courage to bear financial, psychological and social risks due to these new things so that in the future it can make money as a form of satisfaction with the efforts that have been made.

Effect of Transferable Skills, Expertise Competence and Entrepreneurial Interest in Entrepreneurial Readiness

The results of data analysis show that transferable skills, competency skills and interest in entrepreneurship together have an influence on entrepreneurial readiness. This can be seen in the results of the analysis of the coefficient of determination that the variable transferable skills, competency skills and entrepreneurial interest have an influence of 63.2% on entrepreneurial readiness, while the remaining 36.8% is influenced by other variables.

Transferable skills, competency skills and interest in entrepreneurship are included in a series of knowledge and experience. These three variables, if optimized together, will have a good impact on entrepreneurship readiness. This is supported by the statement of Pfeuffer & Scherb [10] that students will have a tendency to apply the knowledge that has been mastered to start a business in accordance with their fields.

To be a person who is ready to build a business, it is very necessary to have a high determination found in someone. There are so many factors that influence that someone is able to become someone who is ready for entrepreneurship. Audet & Couteret, [11] asserted that to be an entrepreneur requires a process that is not short, the process begins with the personal identity concerned (can be through formal or informal education), mindset, and ways of doing things. Apriana et al., [12] added that there are other factors that affect readiness in entrepreneurship including leadership, industry practice experience and motivation in achievement.

A successful entrepreneur has several characteristics. This was conveyed by Heflin [13] which consisted of (1) a strong desire to be responsible; (2) has a high obsession in taking advantage of opportunities; (3) tolerance of risk, multiple meanings and uncertainty; (4) high self-confidence; (5) creative and flexibility; (6) desires to get fast results; (7) has a high energy level; (8) has a high motivation of success; and (9) future oriented.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results of the analysis of research data and discussion of transferable skills, competency expertise and interest in entrepreneurship towards entrepreneurship readiness, conclusions can be drawn as follows:

- There is a significant contribution of transferable skills, expertise competencies and interest in entrepreneurship to entrepreneurial readiness that is equal to 63.2%.
- There is a significant contribution of transferable skills to entrepreneurial readiness that is equal to 26.1%.
- There is a significant contribution of expertise competence to entrepreneurial readiness that is equal to 8.3%.
- There is a significant contribution of interest in entrepreneurship to entrepreneurial readiness that is equal to 28.8%.

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